

ENE — 2019 Conference

6—8 November 2019
Museu Marítim de Barcelona

1st Conference on the
EARLY NEOLITHIC of EUROPE

www.ene2019.org

environment is the lack of stones. Also in dealing with this situation flexible action patterns of the Neolithic communities reveal themselves. Based on selected sites this situation involving flexible adaptation strategies of the Neolithic way of life to such specific and to some extent marginal environments will be discussed.

ORAL PRESENTATION 5

Between the Mediterranean and temperate Europe: new evidence of Early Neolithic subsistence in southern Serbia

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The central Balkans is considered a key region in the spread of agriculture from SW Asia to central Europe. First farmers and herders appeared here by around 6200 BC. The direction from which the new subsistence basis reached the region remains a matter of debate. If it came from the south, then the Axios (Vardar) and Morava river valleys, extending longitudinally through the central part of the peninsula, represented the major route. If the direction from the east was more relevant in the Neolithisation process, then the lower and middle Danube course would have been crucial. Located at the crossroad of these routes, the mountainous region of southern Serbia is central to the debate. However, until recently, only very scarce evidence of the Early Neolithic plant production and animal husbandry has been available from the region, and it mainly included occasional and accidental finds. The new research project conducted by the OREA Institute in Vienna, principally at the site of Svinjarička Čuka in

southeast Serbia, provides first insights into the Early Neolithic occupation in the region, including the information on one of the earliest recorded agricultural activity in the central Balkans. In the paper, we present the investigations at the site and the initial results of zooarchaeological and archaeobotanical analyses, which offer a first glimpse into the Early Neolithic subsistence economy of the region based on the spectrum of plants and animals used by the occupants of the site. We then put our findings into a broader picture for the central Balkans, which brings us closer to understanding of the beginnings of agriculture in what has sometimes been described as a Neolithic 'transit zone'.

ORAL PRESENTATION 6

Dietary adaptations at the Early Neolithic in the Danube Gorges: Neolithized foragers or Mesolithized farmers?

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It is now considered that migrants originating from Near-Eastern Neolithic communities brought the farming way of life into Europe, reshaping then the ecological niche, the socio-cultural organization, as well as major bio-demographic features. Although the Neolithic expansion is well-documented at a regional level, the nature and consequences of local interactions with foragers are still debated. The Danube Gorges prehistoric